

How structural homophobia is spreading HIV-risk sexual behaviours around the world

Vincent Leroy^{a,*}, Erik Lamontagne^{c,d}, Bruno Spire^a, Sean Howell^b, Sylvie Boyer^{a,1}, Bruno Ventelou^{d,1}

^a Aix Marseille Univ, Inserm, IRD, SESSTIM, Sciences Economiques & Sociales de la Santé & Traitement de l'Information Médicale, ISSPAM, France

^b LGBT+ Foundation, San Francisco, CA, USA

^c UNAIDS, Johannesburg, South Africa

^d Aix-Marseille University, CNRS, EHESS, Centrale Marseille, Aix-Marseille School of Economics, France

ABSTRACT

Although discrimination and stigma are recognised determinants of HIV-risk sexual behaviours in the LGBTI population, related data are scarce. In particular, the 'pathways' between these determinants and HIV-risk sexual behaviours are understudied. The main objective of the present study was to fill this knowledge gap by analysing – in a worldwide sample – the relationships between multiple dimensions of homophobia, general propensity to take risks, and HIV-risk sexual behaviours. We used data from UNAIDS's Global LGBTI Happiness survey, which was conducted among 115 000 individuals in 204 countries in 2019/2020. Structural/institutional homophobia is defined at the country level and was measured mainly by assessing the number and type of restrictive institutional laws and homophobic attitudes. Structural equation modelling was performed to identify associations between different dimensions of homophobia and HIV-risk sexual behaviours in participants who self-identified as cisgender, transgender, nonbinary, intersex, gay, bisexual and queer. In our worldwide sample of 69 640 participants, we found that structural homophobia predicted local homophobia ($\beta = 0.040$, (95 %CI = 0.027–0.053)), homophobia at work ($\beta = 0.022$, (95 %CI = 0.010–0.034)), family homophobia ($\beta = 0.19$, (95 %CI = 0.18–0.20)), and HIV-risk sexual behaviours ($\beta = 0.069$, (95 %CI = 0.059–0.078)). Results indicate that local homophobia and homophobia at work were directly and positively associated with HIV-risk sexual behaviour ($\beta = 0.088$, (95 %CI = 0.072–0.10) and 0.013, (95 %CI = 0.001–0.026), respectively). Institutional (/structural) homophobia was also indirectly associated with general risk-taking and HIV-risk sexual behaviour, mediated by individual homophobia. Our findings suggest that structural homophobia was associated with HIV-risk sexual behaviours through both direct and indirect pathways. In the context of limiting HIV-risk sexual behaviours, within the bigger picture of curbing the HIV epidemic, it is essential to prioritize implementing policies which eradicate homophobic violence, and which defend the rights of sexual and gender diverse people.

1. Introduction

"If we do not appreciate the nature and impact of stigma, none of our interventions can begin to be successful. AIDS is probably the most stigmatised disease in history." (Edwin Cameron, 2007).

Sexual and gender diverse (SGD) people are one of the key populations at high risk of HIV acquisition. In Africa, it is estimated that men who have sex with men (MSM) are approximately four times more likely to be infected than the general population (Beyrer et al., 2010). In 2016, the USA's national public health agency (i.e., Centers for Disease Control and Prevention) estimated that over half of seropositive people in the country were gay or bisexual men (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2016). Moreover, HIV prevalence in adult transgender

women (TG) is 20 times higher than in non-TG adults (UNAIDS fact sheet). Studies suggest that the burden of HIV acquisition in TG in high- and middle-income countries is substantial; there are few data on this subject for low-income countries (Baral and Phaswana-Mafuya, 2012, Baral et al., 2013; Stutterheim et al., 2021). The literature highlights that the risk factors responsible for the high prevalence of HIV acquisition among sexual and gender diverse people are both structural and individual in nature; they include unprotected anal sex, difficulties related to access to treatment, a lack of knowledge about HIV transmission, the use of drugs, economic insecurity, and stigma and discrimination (Beyrer et al., 2012). In this article, we will attempt to demonstrate that individual factors and structural determinants are not independent; individual decisions to expose oneself to risk are generally the result of psychological processes that are themselves deeply

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: vincent.leroy2@inserm.fr (V. Leroy), lamontagne@unaids.org (E. Lamontagne), bruno.spire@inserm.fr (B. Spire), sean@hornet.com (S. Howell), sylvie.boyer@inserm.fr (S. Boyer), bruno.ventelou@univ-amu.fr (B. Ventelou).

¹ These two last authors contributed equally

determined by the context in which the decision is made. This conceptualization resonates with the UNAIDS 10-10-10 goals on societal enablers, which call for the reduction of punitive laws, stigma and discrimination, and gender-based inequalities to less than 10 % globally by 2025 (UNAIDS, 2017). These goals highlight the central role of structural and individual determinants in shaping vulnerability to HIV acquisition. Furthermore, beyond HIV-related risk behaviours, studies have shown that structural-level conditions such as political or economic pressure can influence individuals' propensity to take risks (Zinn, 2015), thereby supporting the idea that macro-level factors shape micro-level behaviour. In parallel, research on minority stress indicates that stigma and discrimination - particularly among SGD - function as chronic stressors or forms of adversity that can affect psychological mechanisms related to impulse control, sensation seeking, and general risk-taking, not solely sexual risk-taking (Hatzenbuehler, 2009; Meyer, 2003). Literature linking adverse experiences and trauma to impulsivity further reinforces the plausibility of such pathways.

Despite progress in social and legal recognition of the LGBTI population in most Western countries, homophobia continues to be an issue in societies worldwide. There are still 64 countries where same-sex sexual acts between adults in private are illegal (ILGA, 2020). Thirty-one of these countries are in Africa, where structural homophobia is very present. There are several possible reasons for this, including religion, globalisation, resistance to the West, rhetoric from leaders and colonialism (Ireland, 2013). Structural homophobia diminishes the rights of gay people, making them more vulnerable than heterosexuals; this vulnerability can lead to increased transmission of sexually transmitted diseases (STDs), including HIV. For example, an antigay bill in Uganda in 2009 proposed the introduction of the death penalty for gay people who had sex while living with HIV. The proposal had two serious effects: a decrease in the rate of HIV-testing among gay people, and the cessation of development aid from several foreign countries. The consequence of these effects was an increase in HIV transmission prevalence (Roehr, 2010). In addition, given the severe legal outcomes of same-sex sexual acts in many African countries, a substantial proportion of sexual minorities are forced to hide their sexual orientation, marry women and have children (Anyamele et al., 2005). The consequence of this is an increase in HIV transmission rates in the general population. These phenomena are not limited to African regions. For instance, in Eastern Europe, Asia and the Pacific and Latin America region, several countries, including Russia, China, Indonesia and Paraguay, have banned freedom of expression and/or association regarding LGBTQ + issues. Consequently, governments reduced the dissemination of information and awareness of the challenges faced by these populations, including information about HIV acquisition. Studies show that a lack of knowledge in HIV is associated with an increased risk of transmission and acquisition of the infection (Parker and Rüütel, 2010). From European politicians banning gay pride marches in several countries (Holzhacker, 2013), to hate speeches from African leaders towards homosexual people (Ireland, 2013), authorities tend to spread homophobia in public opinion. Through these repressive actions, governments legitimise homophobia in society as a whole and foster homophobic thoughts and behaviours within population. In what follows, we use the term 'homophobia' to encompass all forms of stigma and discrimination based on sexual and gender characteristics. In this sense, homophobia refers to the stigmatization and discrimination of any non-heterosexual behaviour, identity, relationship, or community.

Homophobia at the individual level has several sources; these are i) cultural: most societies consider heterosexuality to be a social norm and some people fear what is abnormal; ii) religious: although it is uncertain whether the Qur'an or the Bible reject homosexual practices, many religious leaders are against homosexuality; iii) based on political ideology and media manipulation: some populist leaders exploit narratives from heterosexuals who had unpleasant experiences with gay people in order to express negative attitudes towards them for political benefit (Herek, 1986). Sexual and gender minorities are more exposed to verbal

and physical abuse than heterosexual people (Flores et al., 2020; Brown and Herman, 2015; Jaffray, 2018) and are more likely to suffer from mental health deterioration. This is echoed in minority stress theory (MST) (Meyer, 1995, 2003), which posits that stigma and discrimination (and therefore homophobia) cause disproportionate levels of stress for people who suffer from them, and this may lead to health problems. More specifically, studies have shown that psychosocial stress increases risk-exposure, including HIV-risk sexual behaviours (Burchell et al., 2010; Calzavara et al., 2012; Wong et al., 2009). This psychopathological pathway may explain the relationship between homophobia and HIV transmission. This relationship might be explained through another pathway: self-esteem; several empirical studies have shown that homophobia is positively associated with low self-esteem and condomless anal sex in non-heterosexual people (Jamieson et al., 2013; Jeffries et al., 2013; Zervoulis et al., 2015). In our modelling, we will use an original assessment of (self-reported) risk behaviours, drawn from the behavioural science literature (Falk et al., 2018).

In MST, Meyer postulates that minority stress is a consequence of the cumulative impact of the minority individual's experiences within a dominant society, suggesting that both structural and individual discrimination coexist (Meyer, 1995, 2003). Taken separately, there is evidence that these two forms of discrimination contribute to a deterioration of minority health (Aho et al., 2014; Hatzenbuehler et al., 2024; Jeffries et al., 2013; Lamontagne et al., 2024; Pascoe and Laura, 2009). One avenue for more detailed research into these two mechanisms would be to investigate the potential interactions and intersections between structural and individual levels of homophobic stigma. In terms of interaction, one could, for example, investigate the plausible hypothesis that there is an interaction between laws that restrict the rights of LGBTI people at the structural level and the propensity of people in society, at the individual level, to hold negative attitudes towards them. In terms of intersectionality, one could investigate how sexual and gender minorities are subjected to structural and individual systems of oppression (Meyer, 2003). In the context of HIV-risk sexual behaviours, structural and individual homophobia may work interdependently to foster them. For example, in a sample of HIV-positive women, Logie et al. found intersections between structural and individual stigma at the structural and individual levels through homophobia, transphobia, racism and HIV-related stigma (Logie et al., 2011). This implies the need for an analysis that consider plausible pathways between each level of stigma, based on empirical evidence from different contexts around the world in terms of criminalization and structural homophobia.

The literature highlights several limitations in studies investigating the relationship between homophobia and HIV-risk sexual behaviours: i) samples sizes are relatively small and cover a very specific geographic area; this limits the representativeness of quantitative results; ii) gender diverse people (i.e., transgender) are under-represented; iii) there is a critical lack of data on developing countries; iv) homophobia is measured at either the individual or contextual level, which excludes pathways between these two levels. A recent systematic review identified 98 articles which analysed the relationship between LGBTI-phobic structural stigma at the country, state, county, census, college or school levels, and health outcomes among LGBTI populations (Hatzenbuehler et al., 2024). None explored the potential pathways linking structural homophobia, individual homophobia on the one hand and exposure to risk and HIV-risk sexual behaviours on the other. Moreover, none investigated data on developing countries. Such an investigation could provide novel insights into the way institutional and social environments directly impact health behaviours. In turn, such findings could help inform and refine public health policies by identifying vulnerable groups and showing how a more inclusive social environment could reduce HIV-risk sexual behaviours. They might also help develop and strengthen MST, through the contribution of original empirical results.

In this context, we investigated the relationships between homophobia at the country and individual levels, and HIV-risk sexual

behaviours. The main hypotheses tested were whether different forms of discrimination influence SGD people's propensity to take risks in life in general and in HIV-risk sexual behaviours context, specifically unprotected anal sex with casual partners. In line with the literature, we assumed and tested that individuals exposed to discrimination because of their gender identity and/or sexual orientation are likely to be psychologically damaged, possibly resulting in excessive levels of stress and/or loss in self-esteem, both of which could foster risk-exposure in their sexual behaviours.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study design and data sources

Data were obtained through UNAIDS's Global LGBTI Happiness Survey which was conducted in 2019/2020. The survey was distributed worldwide through global and national social networks, mainly dating applications, civil society organizations, and activists. The survey was primarily promoted through instant messaging and banner advertising on national and transnational websites, as well as notifications on mobile applications and social networking websites, with the support of various UN agencies and international partners present in participating countries. In total, 253 national and transnational CSOs, NGOs, CBOs and transnational organizations, 25 social networking applications and websites, 16 Global Fund project implementation units, 38 UNDP country offices, 13 CDC country offices, and 70 UNAIDS regional and country offices were contacted.

The Global LGBTI Happiness Survey was developed through a consultative process with representatives of the LGBTI community, sociologists, epidemiologists, and health economists. This process was chosen in order to identify relevant variables; it was complemented by a review of existing tools in the literature. Following this, the survey questionnaire was pilot tested to ensure its acceptability within the LGBTI community. Information collected included sexual orientation, gender identity, socioeconomic vulnerabilities, well-being, HIV-related indicators (serological status, access to HIV services and treatment, HIV-risk sexual behaviours), time preference and risk aversion (in general), stigma and discrimination, self-assessment of social standing and self-perceived health status. The final sample included data for 115 807 participants from 204 countries.

2.2. Study population

The study population for the present analysis included participants in the Global LGBTI Happiness survey aged at least 18 years old who self-identified as cisgender, transgender, non-binary, intersex, gay, bisexual or queer, and who were at risk of acquiring HIV (and, as such, defined as "key populations" by UNAIDS; UNAIDS, 2024a,b). We decided not taking into consideration the behaviour of people who are already HIV positive. Accordingly, the following participants were excluded: persons i) under 18 years old; ii) who self-identified as straight and lesbian. Straight people are not affected by homophobia and lesbian people pose a very low risk of HIV acquisition and transmission through sexual-related behaviours. However, it is worth noting that lesbian individuals are not immune to HIV and other STIs. For example, literature show that that women who have sex with women (including lesbians) are more likely to use drugs, which is one of the key risk factors for HIV infection (Degenhardt, 2005; Heinsbroek et al., 2018; Iversen et al., 2015); iii) who self-declared they were HIV positive. Participants with missing values were excluded from our analysis. Therefore, the final study population for the present analysis comprised 69 640 individuals from more than 180 countries and territories (See Fig. 1). Additionally, we want to mention that the LGBTI happiness survey had some filters, meaning that, for example, lesbian participants could not answer to question regarding HIV risk of acquisition. In result, the final study population could not include transgender and non-binary lesbian people.

Fig. 1. Flowchart of study population selection for the present analysis.

2.3. Variables

2.3.1. Exogenous variable of interest

We measured homophobia at the country level using UNAIDS's recently developed homophobic climate index (HCI) (Lamontagne et al., 2018). This two-part indicator measured both institutional and social homophobia in a country:

$$\beta 1 I s H_i = \sum_{n=1}^{11} \gamma_n L_{n,i} + \varepsilon_i \tag{1}$$

$\beta 1 I s H_i$ or institutional homophobia was assessed by a set of eleven laws that characterized the level of institutionalized homophobia of a country. For each country, each law was scored from 1 to 3: 0 if it did not exist, 1 if it existed but was only in force in certain parts of the country, and 3 if it existed and was in force throughout the whole country (score 3). Each law was then weighted and estimated using factor analysis.

$$\beta 2 S o H_i = \frac{1}{n} + \sum_n acceptance_{n,i} + justifiability_{n,i} \tag{2}$$

$\beta 2 S o H_i$ or social homophobia (equation (2)) was measured by examining answers to two questions asked to more than 460 000 respondents representative of the general population in 91 countries in the most recent three waves of the World Values Survey, the 2008 European Values Survey and the Afrobarometer. The first question was: "On this list are various groups of people. Could you please mention any that you would not like to have as neighbours?". A dichotomous response (yes/no) as to whether respondents chose "homosexuals" or not was used here. The second question was "Do you think (homosexuality) can always be justified, never justified, or somewhere in between? Both questions were weighted using factor analysis.

$$HCI = \beta 1 I s H_i + \beta 2 S o H_i \tag{3}$$

The HCI was constructed combining the coefficients of institutional and social homophobia (see equation (3) above). It provided a continuous variable taking values from 0 to 1 for each country, with higher

scores indicating higher levels of both institutional and social homophobia.

For this article, we started from Lamontagne et al., (2018) and we added our own imputation. This second version of HCI, which used multiple imputation techniques, allowed us to consider more countries. To obtain these countries we performed multiple imputation chained equations with neighboring countries having comparable socioeconomic, judicial and political characteristics. When there were no comparable characteristics, the country was not included in the index. The resulting study sample increased, from 67 444 individuals when using the first HCI version, to 69 640 individuals when using the imputed version. We provide standardized direct effects estimation using the original version of HCI (158 countries) in Appendix as a robustness check.

2.3.2. Endogenous mediation variables

Homophobic stigma and discrimination experienced by participants in their local community and at work (i.e., individual level) were estimated using two latent variables, called *Local homophobia* and *Homophobia at work*. The first was measured using two observed variables which identified i) verbal and ii) physical abuse experienced based on sexual orientation and/or gender identity. The second took into account situations of discrimination in the workplace because of sexual orientation and/or gender identity, such as harassment, being asked not to reveal one's gender or sexual orientation, being asked not to work with clients, and having an application for a new position or a promotion refused. Moreover, an observed variable measured discrimination by family members with the following statement: "My family accepts me as I am". Participants who answered "strongly disagree", "disagree" and "I don't know" were considered to be victims of familial homophobia, while those who answered "agree" and "strongly agree" were not considered to be victims of familial homophobia. (The inclusion of 'I don't know' responses in the category of victims of familial homophobia reflects an interpretative choice aimed at capturing uncertainty, non-disclosure, or implicit lack of acceptance within the family environment. This category should therefore be interpreted as indicating ambiguous or uncertain family support rather than overt homophobia.). These three measures refer to experiences of homophobia at an individual level, i.e. individuals who endure discrimination directly. In what follows, when referring to these, we will systematically use the term "individual homophobia".

A measure of the propensity to take risks in general was also added using the following question: "How willing are you to take risks, in general? Answer 0 for not at all willing, or answer 10 for very willing, or answer some place in between." This variable is a well-established measure of economic and social preferences; it has been used for almost all populations worldwide to estimate attitudes toward risk-taking, with an excellent reliability (Falk et al., 2018).

2.3.3. Endogenous outcome variable

We created a 'HIV-risk sexual behaviours' variable (i.e., individual), which was a composite variable measuring insertive and receptive unprotected anal intercourse (UAI) using the following two questions:

- i) "In the past three months, with how many different sexual partners did you have anal sex without any kind of HIV prevention method? That is without a condom, PrEP or an undetectable HIV viral load?" (0; 1, steady; 1, casual; 2; 3 to 10; more than 10).
- ii) "Thinking about the last time you had anal sex without any kind of HIV prevention method (that is, without a condom, PrEP, or an undetectable viral load), did you know the HIV status of your partner? (tick as many as apply)". Possible answers were: i) "s/he is HIV negative; ii) "s/he is HIV positive and undetectable"; iii) "I was on PrEP; s/he was on PrEP"; iv) "I did not ask"; v) "s/he is HIV positive, and I do not know his/her viral load"; vi) "I do not remember"; vii) "Had more than one partner and I do not know everyone's HIV status". We considered that answers iv) to vii) reflected a HIV transmission risk during the most recent anal intercourse.

The 'HIV-risk sexual behaviours' composite variable was assessed as a gradient. The first modality corresponded to overall safe sexual behaviours, that is to say no UAI in the previous three months *and* no HIV transmission risk during the most recent anal intercourse (hereafter 'safe' modality). The second modality corresponded to no UAI in the previous three months *and* at least one HIV transmission risk (i.e., one from iv) to vii) above) (hereafter 'very low' risk) Three other modalities reflected participants who had UAI with, respectively, 1 casual partner, 2–10 partners, and more than 10 partners (hereafter, 'moderate', 'high', and 'very high' risk). An exhaustive description of the variable is available in appendix. This composite 'HIV-risk sexual behaviours' variable should be understood as a self-reported behavioural exposure indicator, based on reported sexual situations and partner-status knowledge, rather than as a direct measure of biological HIV transmissibility.

2.3.4. Exogenous control variables

Finally, we included eight control variables in our model: age, level of education, subjective financial situation (living comfortably, neither living comfortably nor struggling, and struggling on present income) and regional dummies (Asia and Pacific, Eastern Europe and Central Asia, Middle East and North Africa, Sub-Saharan Africa and Latin America and the Caribbean).

2.4. Conceptual framework

This section presents the hypotheses and rationale that served as a foundation for the econometric model we built. Fig. 2 provides an illustration of the hypothetical model, depicting the main relationships between the various measures of homophobia and of risk-related behaviours described in the previous paragraphs.

Fig. 2. Hypothetical model for the effect of homophobia on HIV-risk sexual behaviours.

Hypothesis 1. *Structural homophobia, such as laws that criminalize same sex relationships, normalizes homophobia in the general population, and generates individual discrimination behaviours.*

The methodological approach we took to model the pathway between structural and individual homophobia was based on socio-ecological theory (King et al., 2014; Lamontagne et al., 2025). This theory aims to understand complex interactions between environmental, societal and individual factors that influence behaviours and health outcomes. First, we assumed that structural mechanisms, such as public policies and laws, tend to influence mass behaviour (Tummers, 2019). We also assumed that the implementation of laws that stigmatize individuals based on their sexual orientation and/or gender identity normalizes discriminatory practices. Furthermore, we assumed that a higher HCI value (i.e., structural dimension) predicts greater homophobia at the individual level in the general population. Accordingly, we expected the coefficients of the direct effects between HCI and our three individual-level homophobic variables to be positive.

Hypothesis 2. *Individual homophobia tend to increase the propensity to take risks in general, and increase the propensity for HIV-risk sexual behaviours in SGD people.*

The literature shows that perceived and experienced discrimination is a potential determinant of risk-related behaviours. In a sample of more than two hundred peer-reviewed articles, Benner et al.'s meta-analysis highlighted a positive association between discrimination and greater engagement in HIV-risk sexual behaviours (Benner et al., 2018). In this context, in order to study the possible pathways between individual-level homophobia and HIV-risk sexual behaviours, we assumed that discrimination against SGD people would foster their propensity to take risks in general and HIV-risk sexual behaviours. We expected the coefficients of the direct effects between homophobic variables at an individual level and both risks in general and HIV-risk sexual behaviours to be positive.

Hypothesis 3. *Structural homophobia is directly and indirectly linked to how likely SGD people are to engage in HIV-risk sexual behaviours.*

We assumed that a high degree of structural homophobia would translate into a greater likelihood that SGD people would engage in HIV-risk sexual behaviours. As mentioned above, there are still dozens of countries in the world where consensual same sex sexual acts between adults are prohibited and punishable by imprisonment, physical retribution and death. SGD people who live and evolve in these unfavourable social environments (e.g., clandestine sex, arrest) find themselves in situations of greater risk of HIV acquisition; this may limit how much attention they pay to the health risks of unprotected sex. Pachankis et al. found that greater country-level stigma was associated with a greater likelihood of HIV-risk sexual behaviours in a sample of MSM covering 38 European countries (Pachankis et al., 2015). The direct effect of HCI on the HIV-risk sexual behaviours was expected to be positive. If both this pathway between structural homophobia and HIV-risk behaviours, and hypothesis 2 were confirmed, structural homophobia was expected to indirectly predict HIV-risk sexual behaviours through individual homophobia. Indirect effects between HCI and HIV-risk sexual behaviours were expected to be positive.

Hypothesis 4. *SGD people's propensity for taking risks in general has a mediating effect on homophobia.*

We hypothesized that some of the impact of homophobia is mediated by a greater propensity by SGD people to take risks in general. This was based on the assumption of a psychological pathway, whereby lower self-esteem as a result of discrimination leads to a greater propensity to take risks in general, which in turn fosters HIV-risk sexual behaviours (Fischer and Holz, 2007).

2.5. Econometric model

In order to test our four hypotheses and, more generally, to evaluate

the direct and indirect relationships between the different forms of homophobia outlined above, and SGD people's propensity to take risks in general - with a specific focus on HIV-risk sexual behaviours - we performed structural equation modelling (SEM). This enabled us to consider a set of exogenous and endogenous variables, whereby an exogenous variable is used to predict multiple endogenous variables (Nunkoo and Ramkissoon, 2012). Specifically, we used SEM to perform a mediation analysis assuming that the effect of the exogenous variable on the outcome might vary with the addition of other endogenous explanatory factors (Sardeshmukh and Vandenberg, 2017). The step-by-step process by which the model was formed (which is mainly composed of equations) is provided in the appendix.

To select the best fit model (i.e., the model that best fitted the sample dataset), we tested the following goodness-of-fit indices: the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), the Comparative Fit Index (CFI), the Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI), and the Standardised Root Mean Square Residual (SPMR). The literature provides cut-off values to assess the goodness-of-fit for each of these indices (Hooper et al., 2007); the RMSEA needs to be lower than 0.050, the CFI and TLI greater than 0.90, and the SPMR lower than 0.080. However, these cut-offs reflect a model which only uses continuous variables. There is currently no scientific consensus as regards cut-offs for models including categorical variables, like the one we present here (Xia and Yang, 2019). The majority of cut-offs we used were validated except for TLI, which exhibited a value approaching 0.90 (see results section iii.c).

3. Results

3.1. Descriptive statistics

3.1.1. Description of the study population

Table 1 presents descriptive statistics of our study population. Three quarters self-identified as gay people (76 %), one fifth as bisexual people (20 %), and 4 % as queer people. More than half of participants reported experiencing verbal abuse (59 %) while physical abuse was reported by a fifth (22 %) of participants. Homophobia at work affected in average 4 % of the population studied, and nearly half (47 %) the participants reported familial homophobia.

In terms of their propensity to take risks in general in life, 44 % of the participants indicated a value between 7 and 10 on the 0–10 scale. Forty-five percent declared they engaged in HIV-risk sexual behaviours (i.e. UAI with at least one partner). Two-thirds (69 %) were aged between 18 and 34 years old, 71 % had a university degree (i.e., Bachelor's/Master's/Doctorate), and 35 % reported a stable economic situation (i.e., comfortable, really comfortable with present income). Around one-third (28 %) of participants were from Western Europe and North America, while 10 % were from Africa and the Middle East. Participants from Latin America and the Caribbean represented almost a quarter (23 %) of the sample. The remainder of the sample declared themselves to be from Asian regions and Eastern Europe.

3.1.2. Distribution of the HCI and HIV-risk behaviour variables worldwide

Fig. 3 below represents an overview of the HCI distribution worldwide. As we can see, the African continent - with the exception of South-Africa - and the Middle East, would seem to be the two regions of the world where structural homophobia was the highest. Within South America, higher HCI scores were found for Brazil, Colombia, Paraguay and Venezuela, while Argentina, Chile and Bolivia appeared to be more institutionally inclusive of LGBTI communities. Although Western Europe, North America and Australia had the lowest HCI scores, this does not mean these regions were homophobia-free. It is important to point out that discrimination based on sexual orientation and gender identity is still deeply rooted in all societies worldwide (ILGA, 2020).

Fig. 4 below shows the global distribution of our HIV-risk sexual behaviours variable (the HIV-risk behaviour outcome was recategorized to simplify the visualisation within Fig. 4, see appendix). The

Table 1
Descriptive statistics of the study population (N = 69 640).

Variables	N	% (SD)
Type of homophobia		
Structural level		
HCI index	69 640	(0.15)
Individual level Local		
Verbal insults	41 257	59.2
Physical abuse	15 032	21.6
Work		
Application for new post refused	1792	2.6
Promotion refused	1850	2.7
Harassment	4217	6.1
Asked to not reveal gender/sexual orientation	4037	5.8
Asked not to work with clients	775	1.1
Familial		
Not accepted by family members	33 035	47.4
Risk measures		
Propensity to take risks		
Weak (score 0–3)	13 834	19.9
Moderate (score 4–6)	25 411	36.5
Strong (score 7–10)	30 395	43.7
HIV-risk sexual behaviours		
Safe	29 610	42.5
Very low risk	8797	12.7
Moderate risk	18 490	26.6
Strong risk	11 255	16.2
Very strong risk	1488	2.1
Participant's HIV status (missing = 350)		
Negative	49 027	70.8
Do not want to answer	3125	4.5
Do not know	17 138	24.7
Social identity		
Sexual orientation (missing = 165)		
Gay people	52 578	75.5
Bisexual people	14 198	20.4
Queer people	2699	3.9
Gender identity (missing = 67)		
Non-binary	4439	6.4
Transgender feminine	2201	3.2
Transgender masculine	1354	1.9
Cisgender man	58 406	83.9
Cisgender woman	3173	4.6
Control		
Age (years)		
18–24	22 546	32.4
25–34	25 824	37.1
35–44	12 861	18.5
45–54	5682	8.2
55–64	2160	3.1
65+	567	0.8
Education level		
None	624	0.9
Primary school	1273	1.8
Secondary school	18 143	26.1
Bachelor's degree	36 691	52.7
Master's/Doctorate degree	12 909	18.5
Income		
Really struggling	5691	8.2
Struggling	12 417	17.8
Neither struggling nor comfortable	27 025	38.8
Comfortable	18 038	25.9
Very comfortable	6469	9.3
Region		
Asia and the Pacific	14825	21.3
Eastern Europe and Central Asia	12337	17.7
Middle East and North Africa	3851	5.5
Western and Central Europe and North Am	19527	28
Sub-Saharan Africa	3082	4.4
Latin America and the Caribbean	16018	23

prevalence of these behaviours was higher than the prevalence of safe behaviours in all regions. Among all participants, a global average of 57 % reported that they had UAI with one or more partners in the previous three months and/or that they were at risk during their last UAI. The

regions with the lowest prevalence of HIV-risk sexual behaviours were North America and Europe, while the highest prevalence was reported in the Middle East and African regions.

We can see that regions with the highest prevalence of HIV-risk sexual behaviours tended to be the same regions where the highest levels of structural homophobia were observed. This would suggest that these two phenomena are associated. Statistical modelling is needed to confirm this potential association.

3.2. Inferential statistics

3.2.1. Direct effects

Fig. 5 presents the standardized direct effects. A direct effect of one variable on another is measured by keeping all the other variables of the model constant (while controlling for mediator variables). Since the variables of the model varied in scale, we chose standardization to proportionally describe each association, which decreased substantially magnitude of the estimated coefficient.

The homophobic climate of a country (measured through the HCI) was positively and directly associated with individual-level homophobia. More specifically, holding all other variables constant, a one standard deviation increase in the HCI score corresponded to a 0.022 standard deviation increase in homophobia at work ($\beta = 0.022$, (95 %CI = 0.010–0.034)), 0.040 in local homophobia ($\beta = 0.040$, (95 %CI = 0.027–0.053)) and 0.19 in familial homophobia ($\beta = 0.19$, (95 %CI = 0.18–0.20)). A high degree of HCI score was linked with a higher likelihood of engaging in HIV-risk sexual behaviours ($\beta = 0.069$, (95 %CI = 0.059–0.078)).

As we assumed, the correlation between local homophobia (i.e., verbal and physical violence), and HIV-risk sexual behaviours was positive. A one standard deviation increase in local homophobia was associated with a 0.088 standard deviation increase in HIV-risk sexual behaviours ($\beta = 0.088$, (95 %CI = 0.072–0.10)), and a 0.083 standard deviation increase in the propensity to take risks in general in one's life ($\beta = 0.083$, (95 %CI = 0.069–0.097)).

We also observed a positive direct effect of homophobia in the workplace on general risk taking and engaging in HIV-risk sexual behaviours ($\beta = 0.015$, (95 %CI = 0.003–0.027) and 0.013, (95 %CI = 0.001–0.026)). In contrast, a negative direct effect was observed for familial homophobia on participants' propensity to engage in HIV-risk sexual behaviours ($\beta = -0.023$ (95 %CI = -0.031 to -0.015)). This negative effect was even stronger for people's propensity to take risks in general (-0.089 (95 %CI = -0.097 to -0.082)).

In appendix, we offer two alternative versions of the results shown in Fig. 5:

- a stratification based on the degree of democracy within countries. Fig. 8 shows the model's estimation for countries classified as '(25 % less democratic' (Q1 of World Bank's EIU index), to examine possible variations in causal-path analyses in non-democratic region. As expected, we observed that the direct effect of HCI on HIV-risk sexual behaviours is magnified ($\beta = 0.047$, (95 %CI = 0.034–0.061)) in non-democratic countries compared to the rest of the world ($\beta = 0.023$, (95 %CI = 0.014–0.032)). Fig. 9 shows the model estimation for countries considered more democratic;
- A robustness check which replicates the results using the original version of HCI (available in 158 countries). We observed negligible differences compared to the imputed version, demonstrating the stability of the model across versions. (see Fig. 10).

3.2.2. Indirect effects

An indirect effect represents the path from the exogenous variable (X) to the endogenous outcome (Y) through a mediator variable (M). Indirect effects were measured by multiplying the pathway coefficient of X on M by the pathway coefficient of M on Y.

The indirect effects of the homophobic climate of a country – i.e.,

Fig. 3. Homophobia at the country level (homophobic climate index, HCI).

Fig. 4. The prevalence of HIV-risk sexual behaviours per region worldwide.

structural homophobia – on HIV-risk sexual behaviours were positive mediated through homophobia at work (0.022×0.013) and local homophobia (0.040×0.089), and negative through familial homophobia (0.19×-0.023) and propensity to take risks in general (-0.017×0.089). With regard to the indirect effects of individual-level homophobia on HIV-risk sexual behaviours mediated through a propensity to take risks in general, local homophobia (0.083×0.089) and homophobia at work (0.015×0.089) were positive, while familial homophobia negative (-0.089×0.089).

3.2.3. Total effects

Table 2 depicts the standardized total effects. A total effect represents the overall influence that an exogenous variable (X) had on

outcome variable (Y), considering all possible mediating pathways through which X could affect Y. In other words, it is the addition of direct and indirect effects.

The total effects of homophobia on a person's propensity to take risks in general in life, were positive for local and work homophobia, but negative for country-level homophobia and familial homophobia ($\beta = 0.080$, (95 %CI = $0.063-0.097$), 0.015 , -0.031 , (95 %CI = -0.040 to -0.021) and -0.089 , (95 %CI = -0.097 to -0.081)).

The total effects of homophobia at the structural and individual levels on HIV-risk sexual behaviours, were positive, except for familial homophobia ($\beta = 0.066$, (95 %CI = $0.056-0.075$) 0.099 , (95 %CI = $0.091-0.106$) 0.015 , (95 %CI = -0.002 to 0.031) and -0.031 , (95 %CI = -0.039 to -0.023)). We examine this finding in the next subsection

Fig. 5. Standardized direct effects.

Table 2
Standardized total effects (N = 69 640).

Variables	Coefficient	P> z	[95 % conf. interval]	
HIV-risk sexual behaviours				
Country-level homophobic	0.066	0.000	0.056	0.075
Individual homophobia: local	0.099	0.000	0.091	0.106
Individual homophobia: work	0.015	0.078	-0.002	0.031
Individual homophobia: family	-0.031	0.000	-0.039	-0.023
Propensity to take risks in general in life	0.089	0.000	0.081	0.096
Age	0.053	0.000	0.045	0.061
Education	-0.033	0.000	-0.041	-0.026
Income	-0.031	0.000	-0.039	-0.024
Asia and Pacific	-0.048	0.000	-0.059	-0.038
Eastern Europe and Central Asia	-0.054	0.000	-0.064	-0.044
Middle East and North Africa	0.048	0.000	0.039	0.056
Sub-Saharan Africa	0.006	0.173	-0.003	0.014
Latin America and the Caribbean	0.005	0.313	-0.004	0.014
Individual homophobia: local				
Country-level homophobic climate	0.040	0.000	0.025	0.054
Age	-0.107	0.000	-0.128	-0.087
Education	-0.058	0.000	-0.072	-0.044
Income	-0.211	0.000	-0.247	-0.175
Asia and Pacific	-0.060	0.000	-0.077	-0.043
Eastern Europe and Central Asia	0.048	0.000	0.033	0.064
Middle East and North Africa	0.064	0.000	0.048	0.079
Sub-Saharan Africa	0.125	0.000	0.102	0.148
Latin America and the Caribbean	0.052	0.000	0.037	0.067
Individual homophobia: work				
Country-level homophobic climate	0.041	0.015	0.006	0.076
Individual homophobia: local	0.487	0.020	0.088	0.885
Age	-0.021	0.037	-0.040	-0.001
Education	-0.029	0.024	-0.055	-0.004
Income	-0.138	0.015	-0.250	-0.027
Asia and Pacific	0.018	0.074	-0.002	0.038
Eastern Europe and Central Asia	-0.001	0.202	-0.024	0.005
Middle East and North Africa	0.053	0.018	0.009	0.097
Sub-Saharan Africa	0.039	0.021	0.006	0.072
Latin America and the Caribbean	0.036	0.024	0.005	0.068
Individual homophobia: family				
Country-level homophobic climate	0.197	0.000	0.188	0.207
Individual homophobia: local	0.116	0.000	0.095	0.137
Age	-0.163	0.000	-0.170	-0.156
Education	-0.004	0.286	-0.011	0.003
Income	-0.024	0.000	-0.027	-0.022
Asia and Pacific	-0.046	0.000	-0.048	-0.028
Eastern Europe and Central Asia	0.052	0.000	0.031	0.049
Middle East and North Africa	0.125	0.000	0.049	0.065
Sub-Saharan Africa	0.003	0.754	-0.007	0.009
Latin America and the Caribbean	-0.108	0.000	-0.099	-0.082
Propensity to take risks in general in life				
Country-level homophobic climate	-0.031	0.000	-0.040	-0.021
Individual homophobia: local	0.080	0.000	0.063	0.097
Individual homophobia: at work	0.015	0.000	(base)	(base)
Individual homophobia: family	-0.089	0.000	-0.097	-0.082
Age	-0.052	0.000	-0.060	-0.045
Education	-0.029	0.000	-0.037	-0.022
Income	0.017	0.000	0.010	0.025
Asia and Pacific	0.018	0.000	0.017	0.038
Eastern Europe and Central Asia	-0.072	0.000	-0.082	-0.063
Middle East and North Africa	0.008	0.049	0.000	0.017
Sub-Saharan Africa	0.056	0.000	0.048	0.065
Latin America and the Caribbean	0.146	0.000	0.137	0.155

(iii.b.d.)

Confidence intervals were manually computed, as STATA does not provide them (see appendix). Western Europe and North America was chosen as the reference region because it concentrated the largest proportion of participants and the lowest proportion of structural homophobia.

3.2.4. The relationship between age and familial homophobia

Familial homophobia was negatively associated with a propensity to

Table 3
Goodness-of-fit indices.

Model	RMSEA	CFI	TLI	SPMR
Full	0.032	0.92	0.85	0.019
Age (>24)	0.031	0.92	0.86	0.018
Age (=<24)	0.043	0.91	0.84	0.021
EIU index (Q1)	0.037	0.93	0.88	0.023
EIU index (Q2-Q4)	0.033	0.93	0.88	0.021
Original HCI	0.036	0.93	0.88	0.022

take risks in general and to engage in and HIV-risk sexual behaviours. This was an unexpected finding. We assumed that it would be observed for participants who lived with relatives at the time of the Happiness survey. To study this hypothesis, we ran the model on two sub-samples: i) respondents aged 18–24 years old (n = 22 546); ii) respondents over 24 years old (n = 47 094). The direct, indirect and total effects of familial homophobia were negatively associated with both risk measures for the first cluster and with general propensity only for the second. However, there was less statistical evidence for a correlation between familial homophobia and HIV-risk sexual behaviours in persons aged over 24 years with an estimated coefficient of -0.007 (95 %CI = -0.017 to 0.002, p-value = 0.131) (see [dfg1](#) and [dfg2](#) in the Appendix).

3.3. Goodness-of-fit

We tested several indices to evaluate the goodness-of-fit of our model. [Table 3](#) below presents the results which confirm that our model satisfactorily fit the data.

4. Discussion

The present analysis investigated the pathways between multiple dimensions of homophobia and the likelihood of SGD people engaging in HIV-risk sexual behaviours. By using SEM, we were able to take a wide range of effects into account. This provided us with a greater understanding of the relationships between homophobia at the structural and individual levels, and HIV-risk sexual behaviours. The latter captures risk-exposure contexts and decision-making environments in relation to HIV, and should not be interpreted as reflecting individual-level biomedical vulnerability to HIV infection.

First, our results show that structural homophobia (i.e., at the country level) contributes to predict individual-level homophobic behaviours. More specifically, the strongest direct effect was observed for familial homophobia ($\beta = 0.19$, (95 %CI = 0.18–0.20)), representing a substantively important association as a one standard deviation increase in the HCI score was associated with a one fifth of a standard deviation increase in familial homophobia. The association with local homophobia ($\beta = 0.040$ (95 %CI = 0.027–0.053)) and homophobia at work ($\beta = 0.022$ (95 %CI = 0.010–0.034)) were comparably smaller but not negligible as they operate over a large number of country-level context and a more regulated social environment than the family setting. These findings follow those of Bränström et al., who found that, in a 28-country sample, a larger proportion of sexual minorities living in countries with higher levels of stigma reported victimization than those living in countries with lower levels of stigma (Bränström et al., 2023). By criminalising homosexuality, countries influence the general population's negative behaviour towards SGD people. This would tend to confirm our first hypothesis. However, the question of possible reverse causality needs to be considered. For instance, one could argue that candidates in election proposed homophobic programmes in order to win votes from a general population demanding such programmes. The counter argument is that individual homophobic opinion/attitude is not an innate trait, and that discriminatory attitudes towards one's sexual orientation and/or gender identity have structural origins, such as laws, religious and cultural traditions (Herek, 1986; Ireland, 2013).

Statistically speaking, our argument is the exogeneity characteristics given by the long-term formation of the structural homophobia variable, which predates the measurement of electoral opinions by polls or surveys.

Second, we found evidence that structural homophobia was positively associated with HIV-risk sexual behaviours, confirming our third hypothesis (the direct effect part, in that case). Participants living in countries with higher degree of institutional and social homophobia showed a moderate but consistent increase in HIV-risk sexual behaviours ($\beta = 0.069$ (95 %CI = 0.059–0.078)). There are still 67 countries in the world where consensual same-sex sexual acts between adults are prohibited and punishable by imprisonment, physical retribution, and - in the worst-case scenario - death. Our findings provide a clear message: this means that LGBT individuals who live and evolve in these unfavourable social environments may find themselves in situations of increased risk of HIV acquisition (e.g., through risk-taking in clandestine sex). Structural homophobia might also spread within different institutions. For instance, even in South Africa, where queer communities are more accepted than in the rest of the African continent, LGBTI persons who indicate their sexual orientation experience exclusion and stigma in healthcare centers (Rispel et al., 2011). This phenomenon could discourage these individuals from seeking healthcare and prevention services. As a result, they are potentially less knowledgeable about sexually transmitted diseases in general and are more likely to engage in HIV-risk sexual behaviours. Additionally, structural homophobia may reduce or prevent a proportion of expenditure on HIV prevention and treatment, which could: i) lower awareness of HIV infection, thus increasing risk-related behaviours; ii) reduce access to treatment, leading to less coverage and thus a higher probability of HIV transmission and acquisition. Further analysis revealed that the estimated coefficient of the direct effect between structural homophobia and HIV-risk sexual behaviours was higher in non-democratic countries than in democratic ones. Specifically, we observed that the estimated coefficient was two times larger in non-democratic countries ($\beta = 0.047$, (95 %CI = 0.034–0.061) vs $\beta = 0.023$, (95 %CI = 0.013–0.032)). This supports the hypothesis of a channel through reduced HIV prevention expenditures (non-democratic regimes probably associate a high HCI score with low expenditures – a relationship that is not statistically verifiable, due to a lack of data on HIV prevention expenditures).

Third, our results highlight that local homophobia, and work homophobia, were both associated with a greater propensity of SGD people to take more risks in general (as defined by Falk et al., 2018), and to have HIV-risk sexual behaviours. For comparison, local homophobia exhibited a direct effect on HIV-risk sexual behaviours that was approximately 6 % larger than the effect on general risks ($\beta = 0.088$ (95 %CI = 0.072–0.10) vs $\beta = 0.083$ (95 %CI = 0.069–0.097)). It is widely accepted that discrimination based on race, ethnicity, sexual orientation and gender identity causes psychological harm, including depression and/or anxiety disorder (Schmitt and Branscombe, 2002; Williams et al., 2003). Research has shown that individuals with mental health problems are more likely to engage in HIV-risk sexual behaviours, such as condomless intercourse with casual partners (Coverdale and Turbott, 2000; Díaz et al., 2004; Maclean et al., 2013). Research also indicates that perceived and experienced discrimination have a significant negative impact on an individual's self-esteem (Fischer and Shaw, 1999; Frable et al., 1997; Zervoulis et al., 2015), and that individuals with low self-esteem are less inclined to take care of themselves, and are more likely to engage in HIV-risk sexual behaviours (MacDonald et al. 2002). Our findings reflect these other studies' results, and therefore tend to confirm our second hypothesis.

Fourth, our results highlight that familial homophobia may be associated with a lower probability of younger (i.e., 18–24 years old) LGBTI people engaging in HIV-risk sexual behaviours. Although modest in magnitude, this association was meaningful ($\beta = -0.023$ (95 %CI = -0.031 to -0.015)). This result was unexpected, as other studies found the opposite association. For example, Morris et al. found that young

persons from sexual minorities in three US cities with homophobic family members were more likely to engage in HIV-risk sexual behaviours (Morris et al., 2020). Elsewhere, Dionne et al. showed negative public opinion of homosexuality in a study of 15 African countries (Dionne and Dulani, 2013). It is important to underline that our results reflected worldwide tendencies, and not just those of one country or region. One possible reason for our unexpected finding is that some younger participants experienced a level of familial homophobia that was so strong that they did not engage in any sexual intercourse, resulting mechanically in no HIV-risk sexual behaviours (as the outcome was defined, and considering the initial questionnaire, which prioritizes taking into account the number of partners). Another plausible explanation might come from the fact that individuals who have experienced discrimination are more likely to hide sensitive information. For instance, Nong et al. found that people who had experienced discrimination were more likely to withhold information from healthcare providers (Nong et al., 2022). This may echo to LGBTI individuals who suffer discrimination and prejudice from their families, and who may consequently be more likely to underreport their sexual activities. We also found that the association between familial homophobia and HIV-risk sexual behaviours tends lessened with increasing age, displaying an estimated direct effect of -0.007 (95 %CI = -0.017 to 0.002 , p-value = 0.131) which may reflect an increasing degree of emancipation from family pressure as one gets older.

This study has several strengths. First, this is the first study to explore the correlation between different dimensions of homophobia and HIV-risk sexual behaviours at a global scale, including developing countries that are rarely present in available databases. Second, the use of structural equation modelling enabled us to discover a wide range of effects, which to our knowledge, have not been previously studied. Third, we confirmed previous findings by Melendez-Torres et al. on a sample of nearly 10 000 sexual and gender diverse people from 45 European and central Asian countries; they found that the degree of country-level homophobia was negatively associated with protective sexual health behaviours (Melendez-Torres et al., 2020).

Our structural equation modelling-based analysis demonstrates that structural homophobia is positively correlated with HIV-risk sexual behaviours through direct, indirect, and total effects. This highlights the significant role played by governments implementing discriminatory laws against SGD people in shaping HIV-related risk behaviours. Several countries in various continents with a very high level of institutional stigma, and discrimination towards SGD minorities, also claim to be actively involved in the fight against HIV. Our finding highlights a clear contradiction in the political testimony of these countries. It is untenable for policymakers to pursue the goal of reducing HIV incidence while simultaneously curtailing the rights of those running the highest risk of infection. In addition, our results highlight the role of structural stigma at the beginning of the chain in predicting individual discrimination behaviours and HIV-risk sexual behaviours. Our point is important for policymakers targeting the control of HIV epidemics, even those who do not support sexual freedom. Rather than trying to repress the members of the LGBTI community, our results push to recommend implementing institutional level policies that focus on enhancing the civil rights of sexual and gender minorities and reducing stigma. These institutional changes are generally advocated for the benefit of individuals. Rees, Sabia and Kumpas, using difference-in-difference estimation model, have shown that state-level anti-bullying laws reduce victimization among LGBTQ+ teenagers (Rees et al., 2022). Applying the same approach, Dillbary and Edwards show that anti-discrimination policies relating to housing contributed to reducing disparities between same-sex and different-sex co-applicants (Dillbary and Edwards, 2019). Similarly, Tilcsik found that US state with anti-discrimination law displayed lower rates of discrimination against gay men in the labor market (Tilcsik, 2011). Beyond these reasons (which are sufficient in themselves), we propose a new rationale that might be accepted even by those who remain stuck in a heterosexual normativity; this rationale being to

reduce HIV-risk behaviours by limiting homophobic discrimination at a structural level.

In this paper, we posit the existence of intersections and interactions between structural and individual-level homophobic discrimination. We recommend that, when possible, researchers consider both levels of measurement when analyzing the impact of homophobia on health. Taking this approach will enable researchers to i) propose a more realistic view of homophobia in society; ii) better understand social behaviors and the mechanisms by which sexual risk-taking decisions are made; iii) reduce unobserved heterogeneity and increase the robustness of their estimates.

Our study also has several limitations. First, the data collection process in the 2019–2020 UNAIDS's Global LGBTI Happiness survey mainly involved LGBT dating apps and associations, effectively creating a convenience sample. Accordingly, our analysis only included populations with access to these technologies, which led to selection bias. As a result, it is doubtful that our study population is representative of all SGD people worldwide. For example, we have a small proportion of transgender individuals, which is a hard-to-reach population in surveys, especially with a worldwide survey including countries where being transgender would lead to severe consequences. Additionally, due to certain filters in the LGBTI happiness survey, we had to exclude lesbian participants who pose a non-zero risk of acquiring and transmitting HIV infection. Second, we did not weight our data, as there are no data available in the literature on the country-level estimates of the number of LGBTI people. This limits the representativeness of our findings on a global scale. Third, our latent homophobic variables were novel and created ad hoc for this study (this is needed by the SEM approach); accordingly, they had not been previously validated. However, the observed variables used to estimate them have already been validated in the literature. Fourth, we included only a small number of control variables due to sensitivity of SEM; this may have led to omitted variable bias and therefore under/overestimation of the coefficients. Fifth, variability in terms of socio-political, sociocultural and socioeconomic contexts induces heterogeneity. With over 180 countries and territories included in the UNAIDS's Global LGBTI Happiness survey, participants' understanding of certain concepts raised in the questionnaire may have varied. Sixth, data were self-reported, which suggests bias, especially for sensitive data such as sexual behaviours. In particular, the survey item on partner HIV status explicitly allowed multiple, non-exclusive responses reflecting complex sexual and prevention contexts. For analytical tractability, responses were aggregated into a composite outcome. This approach does not capture the full combinatorial complexity of individual prevention strategies such as PrEP, and should not be interpreted as prioritising one policy response over another. (There is a strong global scientific consensus that pre-exposure prophylaxis (PrEP) provides near-complete protection against HIV acquisition and that viral suppression eliminates transmission risk). Finally, the data are cross-sectional, which implies that the results cannot be interpreted as causal and that the estimated effects should be treated with caution.

5. Conclusion

Our findings revealed positive associations between structural and

Appendix

A1) Computation of standardized confidence intervals for total effects

Standardized standard errors were computed using the following formula:

$$SE_{std} = SE \times \frac{\beta_{std}}{\beta}$$

Standardized confidence intervals were computed using the following formula:

individual homophobia and HIV-risk sexual behaviours. The latter are recognised to be a key determinant of the transmission of HIV among sexual and gender diverse people worldwide, who constitute-using UNAIDS' terms-key populations in the fight against the HIV epidemic.

Homophobia is still very prevalent in societies throughout the world, and the recent political election results in the United States and Europe indicates the risk of a step backwards compared to the progress made in the last two decades; its elimination may be a key step if we wish to truly eradicate HIV. In this context, we encourage policymakers to develop and implement wide-ranging, practical, and effective policies to end homophobia and which promote LGBTI rights.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Vincent Leroy: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Erik Lamontagne:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation, Methodology. **Bruno Spire:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Sean Howell:** Investigation, Data curation. **Sylvie Boyer:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Bruno Ventelou:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Ethics approval/statement

The design of the Global LGBT Happiness Survey used in this study was developed collaboratively by UNAIDS, the LGBT Foundation, the University of Aix-Marseille, the Medical School of the University of Minnesota, representatives of the LGBT community and other stakeholders. The Survey was approved by the Research Board of Ethics of Aix-Marseille University (No. 2019–14-03–004) and the Research Ethics Review Committee of the World Health Organization (No. ERC.0003175). All study methods followed the guidelines and principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and the Sex and Gender Equity in Research (SAGER). Participants had to provide their informed consent prior to accessing the survey. The survey protocol fully complied with the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Participation was voluntary, and no monetary incentive was given to complete the questionnaire. Participants could skip questions or exit at any stage of the questionnaire. Participants who did not provide a numeric value for age or below 18 were excluded from the study. The survey did not collect any identifier or geolocation data although participants could self-report their country of residence.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by: Agence nationale de recherche sur le sida (ANRS) et les hépatites virales, Grant ref number: 22203 PhD fellowship [Leroy]; “France 2030” investment plan managed by the French National Research Agency, Grant ref number: ANR-17-EURE-0020, 2) Excellence Initiative of Aix-Marseille University, Grant ref number: A*MIDEX [Ventelou]. UNAIDS was involved in data collection. UNAIDS, Geneva, Switzerland.

$$IC_{std} = \beta_i \mp 1.96 \times SE_{std}$$

Below, we provide an example for the HCI HIV-risk behaviour pathway:

$$SE_{std} = 0.0404769 \times \frac{0.0655954}{0.5451347}$$

$$\leftrightarrow SE_{std} = 0.00487054$$

$$IC_{1std} = 0.0655954 - 1.96 \times 0.00487054$$

$$\leftrightarrow IC_{1std} = 0.056$$

$$IC_{2std} = 0.0655954 + 1.96 \times 0.00487054$$

$$\leftrightarrow IC_{2std} = 0.075$$

A2) Models stratified by age

Fig. 6. Standardized direct effects (young sample).

Fig. 7. Standardized direct effects (old sample).

A3) Details on the HIV-risk sexual behaviours' variable

The composite variable considers both questions cited in part ii.c.c). Here is their distribution:

i) Number of UAI partners:

“In the past three months, with how many different sexual partners did you have anal sex without any kind of HIV prevention method? That is without a condom, PrEP or an undetectable HIV viral load?” (0; 1, steady; 1, casual; 2; 3 to 10; more than 10).

UAI partners	Freq.	Percent	Cumulative percent
0	35 161	43	43
1, steady	12 406	15	58
1, casual	7,451	9	67
2	6,463	8	75
3 to 10	5,611	7	82
More than 10	1,563	2	84
Does not apply to me	6,551	8	92
Not concerned	6,707	8	100
Total	81 913	100	

ii) Knowledge about serologic status:

“Thinking about the last time you had anal sex without any kind of HIV prevention method (that is, without a condom, PrEP, or an undetectable viral load), did you know the HIV status of your partner? (tick as many as apply)”. Possible answers were: i) “s/he is HIV negative; ii) “s/he is HIV positive and undetectable”; iii) “I was on PrEP; s/he was on PrEP”; iv) “I did not ask”; v) “s/he is HIV positive, and I do not know his/her viral load”; vi) “I do not remember”; vii) “Had more than one partner and I do not know everyone's HIV status”. We considered that answers iv) to vii) reflected a HIV transmission risk during the most recent anal intercourse.

I did not ask	Freq.	Percent	Cumulative percent
No	71 807	72	72
Yes	21 157	21	93
Not concerned	6,707	7	100
Total	99 671	100	
s/he is HIV positive, and I do not know his/her viral load	Freq.	Percent	Cumulative percent
No	92 445	93	93
Yes	519	1	94
Not concerned	6,707	7	100
Total	99 671	100	
I do not remember	Freq.	Percent	Cumulative percent
No	90 765	91	91
Yes	2,199	2	93
Not concerned	6,707	7	100
Total	99 671	100	
Had more than one partner and I do not know everyone's HIV status	Freq.	Percent	Cumulative percent
No	89 982	90	90
Yes	2,982	3	93
Not concerned	6,707	7	100
Total	99 671	100	

iii) Final variable's form:

HIV-risk sexual behaviours' variable	Freq.	Percent	Cumulative percent
Safe	32 675	43	43
Very low risk	9,037	12	55
Moderate risk	19 857	26	82
Strong risk	12 074	16	98
Very strong risk	1,563	2	100
Total	81 913	100	

Here is a description of each modality:

- **Safe:** UAI partners = 0 or UAI partners = Does not apply & (I did not ask = No & s/he is HIV positive, and I do not know his/her viral load = No & I do not remember = No & Had more than one partner and I do not know everyone's HIV status = No).
- **Very low risk:** UAI partners = 0 or UAI partners = Does not apply & (I did not ask = Yes or s/he is HIV positive, and I do not know his/her viral load = Yes or I do not remember = Yes or Had more than one partner and I do not know everyone's HIV status = Yes).
- **Moderate risk:** UAI partners = 1, steady or UAI partners = 1, casual.
- **Strong risk:** UAI partners = 2 or UAI partners = 3 to 10.
- **Very strong risk:** UAI partners = More than 10.

People “do-not-concerned” are drop from the analysis (number = 6707); a robustness check has been done with using a specific modality “not-concerned” in the dependent variable, without noticeable changes in the results.

Fig. 4, recategorization of the outcome note:

Safe behaviour and low risk correspond to the first and second modality of the original outcome. High-risk corresponds to the aggregation of the three last modalities of the original outcome (i.e. moderate, strong, very strong; see above).

A4) Equations of the model

We started the model-building process by introducing the HCI. Measured at the country level, it was integrated into the SEM as a fully exogenous process. Using confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), we then constructed the two latent variables local homophobia (*hl*) and homophobia at work (*hw*), which gave equation (4) (latent model of *hl*) and 5 (latent model of *hw*):

$$hll = \lambda_1.verbal + \lambda_2.physical + \delta_{hll} \tag{4}$$

$$hwl = \lambda_1.harrassed + \lambda_2.hidden + \lambda_3.clients + \lambda_4.application + \lambda_5.promotion + \delta_{hwl} \tag{5}$$

where λ_i is the regression coefficients associated with the observed variables presented in section ii.c, and δ_i the measurement errors. We then introduced local homophobia to the SEM; it was endogenous to the HCI, which gave equation (6):

$$hl = \alpha_1 + \beta_1.HCI + \sum_{j=1}^3 \beta_{2j}.\gamma_{1j} + \varepsilon_1 \tag{6}$$

where β_{ij} is the regression coefficient of the control variables, and γ_{ij} the *j*th control variable. Following this, we introduced homophobia at work and familial homophobia which were both endogenous to the HCI and to local homophobia. Therefore, equations (7) and (8) were estimated as follows:

$$hw = \alpha_1 + \beta_1.HCI + \beta_2.hll + \sum_{j=1}^3 \beta_{3j}.\gamma_{1j} + \varepsilon_1 \tag{7}$$

$$hf = \alpha_1 + \beta_1.HCI + \beta_2.hll + \sum_{j=1}^3 \beta_{3j}.\gamma_{1j} + \varepsilon_1 \tag{8}$$

Subsequently, we introduced the first risk measure, specifically the likelihood of taking risks in general (*ptr*). This was predicted by every homophobic variable already included in the model at this point with the following equation:

$$ptr = \alpha_1 + \beta_1.HCI + \beta_2.hll + \beta_3.hw + \beta_4.hf + \sum_{j=1}^3 \beta_{5j}.\gamma_{1j} + \epsilon_1 \tag{9}$$

Finally, we added the HIV-risk sexual behaviour measure (*hiv*) to complete the SEM model. We posited a direct effect between this variable and all the others this variable and all others, and proceeded to estimate equation (10):

$$hiv = \alpha_1 + \beta_1.HCI + \beta_2.hll + \beta_3.hw + \beta_4.hf + \beta_5.ptr + \sum_{j=1}^3 \beta_{6j}.\gamma_{1j} + \epsilon_1 \tag{10}$$

A5) Models stratified by democratic level

Fig. 8. Standardized direct effects (less democratic countries - quartile 1 of the EIU index).

Fig. 9. Standardized direct effects (rest of the word - other quartiles of the EIU index).

We ran the model on two subsamples using the distribution of the 2019 version of the EIU Democracy Index (The World Bank, 2025). The first sub-sample corresponds to Q1 (25 % less democratic) while the second sub-sample corresponds to the rest of the world.

A6) Estimation using the original version of HCI

Fig. 10. Standardized direct effects (non-imputed version of HCI).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

Aho, Josephine, Hakim, Avi, Vuylsteke, Bea, Semde, Gisèle, Gbais, Honorat G., Diarrassouba, Mamadou, Thiam, Marguerite, Laga, Marie, 2014. Exploring risk behaviors and vulnerability for HIV among men who have sex with men in Abidjan, Cote d'Ivoire: poor knowledge, homophobia and sexual violence. *PLoS One* 9 (6), e99591. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0099591>.

Anyamele, Chukwuemeka, Lwabaayi, Ronald, Nguyen, Tuu-Van, Binswanger, Hans, 2005. Sexual minorities, violence and AIDS in Africa. *Africa Region Working Paper Series No. August*.

Baral, Stefan, Phaswana-Mafuya, Nancy, 2012. Rewriting the narrative of the epidemiology of HIV in Sub-Saharan Africa. *SAHARA J: Journal of Social Aspects of HIV/AIDS Research Alliance* 9 (3), 127–130. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17290376.2012.743787>.

Baral, Stefan D., Poteat, Tonia, Strömdahl, Susanne, Wirtz, Andrea L., Guadamuz, Thomas E., Beyrer, Chris, 2013. Worldwide burden of HIV in transgender women: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Lancet Infect. Dis.* 13 (3), 214–222. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099\(12\)70315-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099(12)70315-8).

Benner, Aprile D., Wang, Yijie, Shen, Yishan, Boyle, Alaina E., Polk, Richelle, Cheng, Yen-Pi, 2018. Racial/ethnic discrimination and well-being during adolescence: a meta-analytic review. *Am. Psychol.* 73 (7), 855. <https://doi.org/10.1037/amp0000204>.

Beyrer, Chris, Baral, Stefan D., Walker, Damian, Wirtz, Andrea L., Johns, Benjamin, Sifakis, Frangiscos, 2010. The expanding epidemics of HIV type 1 among men who have sex with men in Low- and middle-income countries: diversity and consistency. *Epidemiol. Rev.* 32, 137–151. <https://doi.org/10.1093/epirev/mxq011>.

Beyrer, Prof Chris, Baral, Stefan D., van Griensven, Frits, Goodreau, Steven M., Suwat Chariyalertsak, Prof, Wirtz, Andrea L., Brookmeyer, Prof Ron, 2012. Global epidemiology of HIV infection in men who have sex with men. *Lancet* 380 (9839), 367. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(12\)60821-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(12)60821-6).

Bränström, R., Fellman, D., Pachankis, J., 2023. Structural stigma and sexual minority victimization across 28 countries: the moderating role of gender, gender nonconformity, and socioeconomic status. *J. Interpers Violence.*

Brown, Taylor N T, and Jody L Herman. n.d. "Intimate Partner Violence and Sexual Abuse Among lgbt People."

Burchell, Ann N., Calzavara, Liviana M., Myers, Ted, Remis, Robert S., Raboud, Janet, Paul, Corey, Swantee, Carol, 2010. Stress and increased HIV infection risk among gay and bisexual men. *AIDS (London, England)* 24 (11), 1757–1764. <https://doi.org/10.1097/QAD.0b013e32833af7e9>.

Calzavara, Liviana M., Burchell, Ann N., Lebovic, Gerald, Myers, Ted, Remis, Robert S., Raboud, Janet, Paul, Corey, Swantee, Carol, Hart, Trevor A., 2012. The impact of stressful life events on unprotected anal intercourse among gay and bisexual men. *AIDS Behav.* 16 (3), 633–643. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10461-010-9879-5>.

Cameron, E., 2007. Legislating an epidemic: the challenge of HIV/AIDS in the workplace. *ILO Headquarters*.

Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2016. HIV among gay and bisexual men. GLAAD [Fact Sheet]. <https://media.glaad.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/01/10143225/cdc-msm-508.pdf>.

Coverdale, J.H., Turbott, S.H., 2000. Risk behaviors for sexually transmitted infections among men with mental disorders. *Psychiatr. Serv.* 51 (2), 234–238. <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.ps.51.2.234>.

Degenhardt, L., 2005. Drug use and risk behaviour among regular ecstasy users: does sexuality make a difference? *Cult. Health Sex.* 7 (6), 599–614.

Díaz, Rafael M., George, Ayala, Bein, Edward, 2004. Sexual risk as an outcome of social oppression: data from a probability sample of Latino gay men in three U.S. cities. *Cult. Divers Ethnic Minor. Psychol.* 10 (3), 255–267. <https://doi.org/10.1037/1099-9809.10.3.255>.

Dillbary, J. Shahar, Edwards, Griffin, 2019. An empirical analysis of sexual orientation discrimination. *Univ. Chicago Law Rev.* 86 (1), 1–75.

Dionne, Kim, Dulani, Boni, 2013. "Attitudes Toward Homosexuality in Sub-saharan Africa,". April.

Falk, Armin, Becker, Anke, Dohmen, Thomas, Enke, Benjamin, Huffman, David, Sunde, Uwe, 2018. Global evidence on economic preferences. *Q. J. Econ.* 133 (4), 1645–1692.

Fischer, Ann R., Holz, Kenna Bolton, 2007. Perceived discrimination and women's psychological distress: the roles of collective and personal self-esteem. *J. Counsel. Psychol.* 54 (2), 154–164. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-0167.54.2.154>.

- Fischer, Ann R., Shaw, Christina M., 1999. African Americans' mental health and perceptions of racist discrimination: the moderating effects of racial socialization experiences and self-esteem. *J. Counsel. Psychol.* 46 (3), 395–407. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-0167.46.3.395>.
- Flores, Andrew R., Langton, Lynn, Meyer, Ilan H., Romero, Adam P., 2020. Victimization rates and traits of sexual and gender minorities in the United States: results from the national crime victimization survey, 2017. *Sci. Adv.* 6 (40), eaba6910. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.aba6910>.
- Frable, D.E., Wortman, C., Joseph, J., 1997. Predicting self-esteem, well-being, and distress in a cohort of gay men: the importance of cultural stigma, personal visibility, community networks, and positive identity. *J. Pers.* 65 (3), 599–624. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-6494.1997.tb00328.x>.
- Hatzenbuehler, M.L., 2009. How does sexual minority stigma "get under the skin"? A psychological mediation framework. *Psychol. Bull.* 135 (5), 707–730. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0016441>. PMID: 19702379; PMCID: PMC2789474.
- Hatzenbuehler, Mark L., Lattanner, Micah R., McKetta, Sarah, Pachankis, John E., 2024. Structural stigma and LGBTQ+ health: a narrative review of quantitative studies. *Lancet Public Health* 9 (2), e109–e127. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2468-2667\(23\)00312-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2468-2667(23)00312-2).
- Heinsbroek, E., Glass, R., Edmundson, C., Hope, V., Desai, M., 2018. Patterns of injecting and non-injecting drug use by sexual behaviour in people who inject drugs attending services in England, Wales and Northern Ireland, 2013–2016. *Int. J. Drug Pol.* 55, 215–221.
- Herek, Gregory M., 1986. The social psychology of homophobia: toward a practical theory. *Rev. Law Soc. Change* 14 (4), 923–934.
- Holzhaecker, Ronald, 2013. State-sponsored homophobia and the denial of the right of assembly in central and Eastern Europe: the 'Boomerang' and the 'Ricochet' between European organizations and civil society to uphold human rights. *Law Pol.* 35 (1–2), 1–28. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9930.2012.00371.x>.
- Hooper, Daire, Coughlan, Joseph, Mullen, Michael, 2007. Structural equation modeling: guidelines for determining model fit. *Electron. J. Bus. Res. Methods* 6 (November), Ireland, Patrick R., 2013. A macro-level analysis of the scope, causes, and consequences of homophobia in Africa. *Afr. Stud. Rev.* 56 (2), 47–66.
- Iversen, J., Dolan, K., Ezard, N., Maher, L., 2015. HIV and hepatitis C virus infection and risk behaviors among heterosexual, bisexual, and lesbian women who inject drugs in Australia. *LGBT Health* 2 (2), 127–134.
- Jamieson, Jeremy P., Koslov, Katrina, Nock, Matthew K., Wendy, Berry Mendes., 2013. Experiencing discrimination increases risk taking. *Psychol. Sci.* 24 (2), 131–139. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0956797612448194>.
- Jeffries, William L., Marks, Gary, Lauby, Jennifer, Murrill, Christopher S., Millett, Gregorio A., 2013. Homophobia is associated with sexual behavior that increases risk of acquiring and transmitting HIV infection among black men who have sex with men. *AIDS Behav.* 17 (4), 1442–1453. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10461-012-0189-y>.
- King, Megan F., Renó, Vivian F., Novo, Evlyn M.L. M., 2014. The concept, dimensions and methods of assessment of human well-being within a socioecological context: a literature review. *Soc. Indic. Res.* 116 (3), 681–698. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11205-013-0320-0>.
- Lamontagne, Erik, d'Elbée, Marc, Ross, Michael W., Carroll, Aengus, Plessis, André du, Loures, Luiz, 2018. A socioecological measurement of homophobia for all countries and its public health impact. *Eur. J. Publ. Health* 28 (5), 967–972. <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurpub/cky023>.
- Lamontagne, E., Leroy, V., Howell, S., et al., 2025. Homophobia, economic precarity and the well-being of sexual and gender diverse people in a 153-country survey. *Nat Hum Behav.*
- Lamontagne, E., Leroy, V., Yakusik, A., et al., 2024. Assessment and determinants of depression and anxiety on a global sample of sexual and gender diverse people at high risk of HIV: a public health approach. *BMC Public Health* 24, 215.
- Logie, Carmen H., James, LLana, Tharao, Wangari, Loutfy, Mona R., 2011. HIV, gender, race, sexual orientation, and sex work: a qualitative study of intersectional stigma experienced by HIV-positive women in Ontario, Canada. *PLoS Med.* 8 (11), e1001124. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1001124>.
- MacDonald, Tara K., Martineau, Alanna M., 2002. Self-esteem, mood, and intentions to use condoms: when does low self-esteem lead to risky health behaviors? *J. Exp. Soc. Psychol.* 38 (3), 299–306. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jesp.2001.1505>.
- Maclean, Catherine, Xu, Haiyong, French, Michael, Ettner, Susan, 2013. Mental health and risky sexual behaviors: evidence from DSM-IV axis II disorders. *J. Ment. Health Pol. Econ.* 16 (December), 187–208.
- Melendez-Torres, G.J., Noori, Teymur, Pharris, Anastasia, Spiteri, Gianfranco, Garner, Alex, Alba, Beatrice, Bourne, Adam, 2020. Country level homophobia and protective sexual health behaviours among HIV negative or untested men who have sex with men in 45 countries. *AIDS Care* 32 (12), 1589–1593. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09540121.2020.1766662>.
- Meyer, Ilan H., 1995. Minority stress and mental health in gay men. *J. Health Soc. Behav.* 36 (1), 38–56. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2137286>.
- Meyer, Ilan H., 2003. Prejudice, social stress, and mental health in lesbian, gay, and bisexual populations: conceptual issues and research evidence. *Psychol. Bull.* 129 (5), 674. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.129.5.674>.
- Morris, Elana, Balaji, Alexandra B., Trujillo, Lindsay, Raspberry, Catherine N., Mustanski, Brian, Newcomb, Michael E., Brady, Kathleen A., Prachand, Nikhil G., 2020. Family factors and HIV-related risk behaviors among adolescent sexual minority males in three United States cities, 2015. *LGBT Health* 7 (7), 367–374. <https://doi.org/10.1089/lgbt.2019.0317>.
- Nong, P., Williamson, A., Anthony, D., Platt, J., Kardias, S., 2022. Discrimination, trust, and withholding information from providers: implications for missing data and inequity. *SSM Popul Health* 18, 101092. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssmph.2022.101092>. PMID: 35479582; PMCID: PMC9035429.
- Nunkoo, Robin, Ramkissoon, Haywantee, 2012. Structural equation modelling and regression analysis in tourism research. *Curr. Issues Tourism* 15 (8), 777–802. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13683500.2011.641947>.
- Pachankis, John E., Hatzenbuehler, Mark L., Hickson, Ford, Weatherburn, Peter, Berg, Rigmor C., Ulrich, Marcus, Schmidt, Axel J., 2015. Hidden from health: structural stigma, sexual orientation concealment, and HIV across 38 countries in the European MSM internet survey. *AIDS (London, England)* 29 (10), 1239–1246. <https://doi.org/10.1097/QAD.0000000000000724>.
- Parker, R.D., Rüütel, K., 2010. Associations of high-risk behaviour and HIV status with HIV knowledge among persons in Tallinn, Estonia. *Scand. J. Publ. Health* 38 (7), 748–755.
- Pascoe, Elizabeth A., Laura, Smart Richman, 2009. Perceived discrimination and health: a meta-analytic review. *Psychol. Bull.* 135 (4), 531. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0016059>.
- Rees, Daniel I., Sabia, Joseph J., Kumpas, Gokhan, 2022. Anti-bullying laws and suicidal behaviors among teenagers. *J. Pol. Anal. Manag.* 41 (3), 787–823.
- Rispel, Laetitia C., Metcalf, Carol A., Cloete, Allandise, Moorman, Julia, Reddy, Vasu, 2011. You become afraid to tell them that you are gay: health service utilization by men who have sex with men in South African cities. *J. Publ. Health Pol.* 32 (Suppl 1), S137–S151. <https://doi.org/10.1057/jphp.2011.29>.
- Roehr, Bob, 2010. How homophobia is fuelling Africa's HIV epidemic. *BMJ* 340 (May), c2245. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.c2245>.
- Sardeshmukh, Shruti R., Vandenberg, Robert J., 2017. Integrating moderation and mediation: a structural equation modeling approach. *Organ. Res. Methods* 20 (4), 721–745. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1094428115621609>.
- Schmitt, Michael T., Branscombe, Nyla R., 2002. The meaning and consequences of perceived discrimination in disadvantaged and privileged social groups. *Eur. Rev. Soc. Psychol.* 12 (1), 167–199. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14792772143000058>.
- Stutterheim, Sarah E., van Dijk, Mart, Wang, Haoyi, Jonas, Kai J., 2021. The worldwide burden of HIV in transgender individuals: an updated systematic review and meta-analysis. *PLoS One* 16 (12), e0260063. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0260063>.
- The World Bank. (n.d.). EIU digital infrastructure index [Data set]. Data360. Retrieved October 19, 2025, from https://data360.worldbank.org/en/indicator/EIU_DI_INDEX.
- Tilcsik, A., 2011. Pride and prejudice: employment discrimination against openly gay men in the United States. *AJS* 117 (2), 586–626. <https://doi.org/10.1086/661653>. PMID: 22268247.
- Tummers, Lars, 2019. Public policy and behavior change. *Public Adm. Rev.* 79 (6), 925–930. <https://doi.org/10.1111/puar.13109>.
- UNAIDS, 2017. Ending AIDS: Progress Towards the 90-90-90 Targets. UNAIDS, Geneva, Switzerland.
- UNAIDS, 2024a. HIV and transgender and other gender-diverse people: human rights fact sheet series #4. https://www.unaids.org/sites/default/files/media_asset/04-hi-v-human-rights-factsheet-transgender-gender-diverse_en.pdf.
- UNAIDS, 2024b. UNAIDS Terminology Guidelines. Joint United Nations Programme on HIV/AIDS, Geneva, Switzerland. https://www.unaids.org/sites/default/files/media_asset/2024-terminology-guidelines_en.pdf.
- Williams, David R., Neighbors, Harold W., Jackson, James S., 2003. Racial/ethnic discrimination and health: findings from community studies. *Am. J. Publ. Health* 93 (2), 200–208. <https://doi.org/10.2105/ajph.93.2.200>.
- Wong, Carolyn F., Kipke, Michele D., Weiss, George, McDavitt, Bryce, 2009. The impact of recent stressful experiences on HIV-risk related behaviors. *J. Adolesc.* 33 (3), 463. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.adolescence.2009.06.004>.
- Xia, Yan, Yang, Yanyun, 2019. RMSEA, CFI, and TLI in structural equation modeling with ordered categorical data: the story they tell depends on the estimation methods. *Behav. Res. Methods* 51 (1), 409–428. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13428-018-1055-2>.
- Zervoulis, Karyofyllis, Lyons, Evanthis, Dinos, Sokratis, 2015. Stigma and self-esteem across societies: avoiding blanket psychological responses to gay men experiencing homophobia. *BJPsych Bull.* 39 (4), 167–173. <https://doi.org/10.1192/pb.bp.114.048421>.
- Zinn, J.O., 2015. Towards a better understanding of risk-taking: key concepts, dimensions and perspectives. *Health Risk Soc.* 17 (2), 99–114. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13698575.2015.1023267>.
- ILGA : Lucas Ramon Mendos, Kellyn Botha, Rafael Carrano Lelis, Enrique López de la Peña, Iliá Savelev, et Daron Tan, State-Sponsored Homophobia 2020: Global Legislation Overview Update (Geneva: ILGA, December 2020).